

Publishing articles with integrity: a scenario

Peter is a PhD-student, working on funerary art in Spain, and an editor of a journal on the archaeology of Spain. Peter wants to publish an article, which would well fit into this journal. He does not want to create editorial conflicts, and therefore, discusses his potential publication on the editorial board. They do not see any problems in publishing their research with their journal, and two other editors say that they will review Peter's work without any biases.

Peter submits his paper and, although the discussion of his work during the editorial meeting is uneasy, he is glad that it is provisionally accepted for publication. Subsequently, Peter's paper is sent to two peer reviewers for a double-blind review. There is a difficulty here: Peter has access to the journal's mailbox. Even though the editors have not told him what researchers they were going to ask, he recognizes the names of people who do similar research. He knows that his paper is the only one about funerary art in the current issue, so this concerns his paper.

Peter feels uncomfortable that he knows this and that he closely works with a reviewer. He is fairly sure that at least this peer reviewer will recognize the paper as his research, which might also influence their judgement of the paper. He realizes that he cannot do much about this, as he works in a highly specialized field, and he did not influence the other editors by suggesting names for peer review.

Questions

1. Is there a (editorial) conflict when reviewing Peter's paper? Did Peter influence the review of his paper because he is an editor of this journal?
2. Should the journal change its guidelines so that current editors cannot publish their papers in the journal? What are the advantages and disadvantages of these rules?
3. Does Peter have to tell the other editors (or even peer reviewers) that he knows who is reviewing his paper?
4. Should peer reviewers tell the editorial board that they have recognized the author from the paper and that they decline to do peer reviews? Does this need to be included in the email sent by the editors to the potential peer reviewer?
5. What are the reasons for Peter to withdraw his paper from being published by the journal and to choose another less specialized journal? What are the reasons for not doing so?